

ISic3365

I.Sicily inscription 3365

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building (?)

Material

limestone (?)

Object

architrave (?)

Editor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

02.10.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

EuBoia

Place of origin (modern)

Licodia Eubea

Provenance

via V. Cordova, in reuse in a Byzantine tomb

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 22729

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644870

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
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